

IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL & MENTAL WELL-BEING IN WORK LIFE BALANCE**Dr. Sandeep Sadashivrao Shinde**

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Abstract

Work-Life balance is analytical question which every employee is facing from generation. Physical fitness to carry on the task assigned to him or psychological stress to withstand the load is the major issue to accomplish the final result with contentment is vital. The antecedent set up is gently hampering the desired management of physical & mental wellbeing in work-life of the employee. Mental well-being of a breadwinner is a pre-requisite for their productive accomplishment. Work-related stress could also boldly states that major and minor illnesses; as well as psychological effects can give a negative impact to the life of the employee in the long run. In today's cutthroat competitive world of job there is a gigantic marathon in proving oneself among others which lead to negligence of health and social life. Work-life balance (WLB) refers to the ability of individuals to pursue successfully their work and non-work lives, without unnecessary burdens from one domain undermining the acceptable experience of the other. (M. Noon. & Blyton, 2007).¹ This paper has focus on importance of physical & mental wellbeing in maintaining work-life balance by undertaking simple task in your daily routine which will to lead to diminishing the stress level with positive approach.

Keywords: Physical Well-being, Mental Well-being & Work Life BalanceAarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/amierj/>**Introduction**

Work-life is about shaping and retaining the high quality by motivating, encouraging, supporting, flourishing work environment and conditions where employees can at ease be able to balance between work and personal responsibilities and thus build up employees' loyalty and productivity with devotion. Work life leads to profuse physical and mental health dilemma if unsolved at a given period of time. Lengthy working hours and immense pressure or died line leading to hamper employees' health physically and mentally. This situation gives rise to many health risk factor employee high is at stake. Indulging in bad habits like smoking and alcohol consumption, depression and work to family conflict is also a part and parcel of it.

Objective

The objective of the research is to study the importance of physical well-being and mental well-being in maintaining the work life balance, which plays a core role in leading a successful professional growth environment.

Literature Review

Dhas D (2015). The study revealed that the experts can benefit their companies to capitalize by using work/life drive to

achieve a good return in the marketplace for human resources. Work-life balance has invariably been a valuable asset for the working growth and to give better quality of life to the employees.

Kashyap, S., Joseph, S and Deshmukh G.K (2016). Authors have worked on a descriptive research by analysing the data gathered through secondary sources and considered their viewpoints. The key findings highlight that employees are a treasure to an organisation and need to satisfy their needs and which may be pre-owned by high quality results.

Rao, R and Sharma, U (2018). The aim of this paper is to propose a framework to understand work life balance, the significance and problems faced by various professions and to find out the consequences of Work Life Balance on distinct aspects related to physical, occupational, emotional, social, spiritual and environmental well-being of employees. Motivating the employees and paying good dividend. Employee can be a great asset to increase productivity.

Issahaku, Nkyi and Dramanu (2020). The study investigated that the work life balance of the staff members of the university has a powerful collision on wellbeing. It was suggested that counselling and other psychological tools offered by the counselling centre of the university gave a positive impact to the staff members who were facing difficulties in associating with their work life.

Scope

The arena were employees performance daily task to earn his bread and butter should be motivating, appreciating his hard work, supportive, and encouraging creativity. If employees are constantly working under pressure, the negative impact can be noticed on physical and mental well-being. Majority of time of the employees are spend in the workplace, so to get fruitful result and flourish in the business employer's so to keep employees fit and fine which is the his prime responsibility of the employer. Employers must acknowledge and be cognizant to the physical well-being and mental well-being requisition of employees, both to and fro of the workplace. Formula to be successful in every walk of life whether relationship with employees or family is to respect and care to get outstanding results.

Research Methodology

Research design is descriptive in nature. The research process has been carried out by reviewing literature related to the research problem faced the employees and analysing it. Secondary data has been collected for research purpose from books and research journals and articles that are related to the research problem.

Physical Well-being

Transmittable good personal interest of your physical health is sustainable to have a positive effect on your mental wellbeing and inversely beneficial. If you toss the side, however, if one refrains, then the other brings out the same result, too. Good physical health can alleviate the symptoms happiness and on other side depression will be knocking the door if lack of fitness, while mental health disorders can also escort to aggravate the physical health. This inherent relationship is a mechanism to stay physically and mentally healthy throughout your life. However, ample of people make many attempt to take care of their health and due to various reasons.

Fig: 1.1 Health Habit for Physical Well-being

People need to be trained to avail the leisure time and promote more health programs activities to keep themselves fit and fine. A good exercise programme can guide them to utilise their time and money for a healthy future.

Mental Well-being

Mental well-being is as valuable an asset of an individual as worthy as to remain physically healthy. A mentally flawless person discharges his duties well in time at his workplace. It influences to work more systematically and in a well-organised way which embellishes his retentiveness, drive towards success, positively coping up with a problem as a challenge rather than complaining as these qualities are pre-requisite for the productive performance at work. Mental health problems have an impact on employers and businesses directly through increased absenteeism, negative impact on productivity and profits, as well as an increase in costs to deal with the issue.²

Work-related mental pressure is a sizable root cause of occupational ill health, inadequate productivity and human transgression. These factors lead to raised sickness, immense employee turnover and inadequate performance in the organisation and increase in accidents owing to human error. Work-related stress could also manifest as heart disease, back pain, headaches, gastrointestinal disturbances or various minor illnesses; as well as psychological effects such as anxiety and depression, loss of concentration and poor decision making.³

Mental well-being is essential as physical well-being. Positive mental well-being enables to perform daily functions and responsibilities in a well-ordered manner, acquire voluntarily social connections, affirmative self-content and be better able to cope with life's ups and downs.

Fig: 1.2 Keys ways employers can support employee’s mental health in the work place

Minor suggestions can accomplish a great difference if implemented in every walk of life to retain mental and physical well-being.

- Exercise or walking in your daily routine
 - An increase in physical fitness will reduce the risk of premature death, and a decrease in physical fitness will increase the risk.⁴ so, exercise will keep the physical and mental disorder at bay.
- Boosting happiness by spend time with friends
 - Nothing can replace the time you spend with loved ones and people you trust. Stress level is reduced.
- Pick Someone to talk to
 - Friends, parents or grandparents or anyone to whom you are comfortable with. This reduces the pressure in body and mind.
- Cut down on alcohol
 - Quench your thirst with water or fruit juice, Limit your drinking habit by placing no alcohol at home, Peer pressure can be controlled by saying no politely. Keep busy by setting goals and planning will help to guard your temptation. Engage yourself with new and healthy ways to cope with stress by taking up music or dance or anything which makes to happy.
- Avoid illicit drug use
 - Look at life’s big picture and place the priorities in sequence. To know what harm can it cause to your body and others around you.
- Keep active and eat well
 - Spend time in doing exercise which the highest investment for your life.
- Develop new skills and challenge your capabilities
 - You are never too old to learn anything new; Age should not be a barrier. Education of learn is a lifelong process nothing will be a waste.
- Relax and enjoy your hobbies
 - Time to enjoy your life is also important. Whether it is gardening or reading books or listening to music.

- Set realistic goals
 - Set a goal which will be achievable and have a positive attitude to accomplish it. Failure is just a stepping stone to reach out in other way.

Relationship of Physical and Mental Well-being

Mental and Physical health is basically associated with each other which have an impact on the people quality of life. Any one of the well-being among them is in trouble, the whole body is affected. Here the demands on health care and mental care comes into picture. The world health Organisation (WHO) defines: health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. The WHO states the “there is no health without mental health.”⁵ There is no point to argue who is superior whether physical well-being or health well-being. The associations between mental and physical health are unchallengeable:

- affects Lacking sufficient mental health may lead to chronic physical conditions.
- A chronic physical condition mental health.

To prevent the above chronic condition few keys aspects much be included in to our day to day life route.

- Moderate physical activity,
- Proper dietary habits
- Social Networking and
- Social support of families and friends.

This build up opportunities to reinforce protection factors and curtail the risk factors associated with mental and physical well-being. There should be a fine tuning between the mind and the body which results better work life balance. It is also found to be a significant predictor of job satisfaction. The average working class should have good mental and physical well-being, will experience better work life balance.

Work Life Balance

Fig: 1.3 Depicting Work Life Balance

A “good” work-life balance is explained as a state in which workers feel that they are capable of balancing their work and non-work commitments, and, for the most part, do so. (F. Moore, 2007).⁶ A poor work-life balance can be seen as a

work-related stressor and previous examinations show an association between work-life imbalance and stress responses, such as elevated blood pressure, heart rate and cortisol levels.⁷

1. Job satisfaction is also been found to be a significant predictor of turnover and turnover intention.⁸
2. The average working class people face this problem which is dealing with arduous boss. By improving communication skills can solve this problem to a great extent.
3. Dealing with difficult co-workers can be resolved by an amicable discussion and mutual agreement.
4. Individuals are struggling to find the right balance between work and family responsibilities.⁹ Allotting equal time to work and home can solve to reduce the stress level.
5. Excessive travelling, added on workload, prolong working hours, cut throat competition and small package of salary, can actually leave the physical and mental well-being at stake. Need to overcome all this hurdles by the support of employer.
6. The better work-life balance suggests that the reconciliation policies should be adopted to experience the benefits of a balanced work and domestic life.

Work life balance is an important aspect of a health work environment. Having physical and mental well-being contributes maintaining healthy work life balance which helps to reduce stress and to prevent burn out in the work place. By creating a work environment that prioritizes work life balance. Employers can save money and maintain a healthier and more productive work force.

Discussion

The approach of an employer towards his employee plays a significant role to establish his business for a long run. Reconstructing work-life balance of the employee comprises of flexible working hours, no working on weekends and promoting vacation so that employees can spend time with family members, job-sharing, telecommuting and child-care support. These prerogative ideas allow employees to have charge over their lives, empowering them to be more productive and in comfort zone. Work extra hours only bring about acrimony over the long term. Work for the employer who cares for physical well-being and mental well-being in your long term career.

Conclusion

The issue of mental and physical well-being in maintaining work life balance has become apparent a core topic in the organisation. This study emphasizes the requirement to recognize the requisite of the balance between work and life and manage oneself physically and mentally fit to do daily task in energetic way at work place creating a flexible work environment is one of the best way to satisfy the work life balance of most employees. It is important for employers to realise that work life balance is about having good mental and physical well-being and should strive to improve the overall work place experience of their employees. Prioritizing a healthy culture and cultivating a happy working place promotes work life balance. When employees are happy in their roles, work will feel more like a second home and less like working for a pay cheque. Employers should prioritize comfortable office conditions opportunities for professional growth and opportunities of for social connection.

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